

ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF THE CONTROL AND AUDIT INSPECTION DEPARTMENT OF THE MIA OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article discusses the definitions of personnel management, the selection of law enforcement officers, the features of serving in law enforcement structures, as well as the organizational and legal framework for the control and auditing inspection of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *personnel management, law enforcement agencies, staff performance assessment, motivation, staff satisfaction, efficiency, performance management, civil service.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ПРАВОВАЯ ОСНОВА КОНТРОЛЬНО-РЕВИЗИОННОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ МВД РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются определения управления персоналом, отбор сотрудников правоохранительных органов, особенности прохождения службы в правоохранительных структурах, а также организационно-правовые основы контрольно-ревизионной проверки МВД Республики Узбекистан.*

Ключевые слова: *управление персоналом, правоохранительные органы, оценка деятельности персонала, мотивация, удовлетворенность персонала, эффективность, управление эффективностью, государственная служба.*

INTRODUCTION

The decisive changes that have taken place in the life of our people over the past 5 years have largely changed the worldview and outlook of our society on public administration. In particular, there is a need to introduce modern approaches aimed at ensuring relations in politics, the economy, the administrative and political sphere, including the sphere of law and order.

Over the years, many scientists have given essentially similar definitions of management [1]:

- purposeful and purposeful activity, during which people seek to influence any social system (object, process, phenomenon), change its properties in the necessary direction, bring it into line with the objective laws operating in this environment (V.D. Malkov, G. G. Zuikov);

- external expression of the activity of the subject of control (as well as the behavior of the control system), which consists in providing a targeted impact on the control object in order to cause an expedient transformation of the system or, on the contrary, prevent an inappropriate transformation (V.T. Tomin);

- activities designed to ensure order, normal and effective cooperation of people (Yu.M. Kozlov, E.S. Frolov);

- the process of influencing the system to transfer it from one state to another or maintain it in the established mode (A.P. Korenev);

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS.

In modern conditions, from the position of management, this is the process of designing and innovating social organizations, motivating people to work to achieve the goals of the organization, which is often considered as the art of management.

The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an integral part of state executive bodies that carry out a special type of public service.

In the system of state bodies, the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs traditionally refers to law enforcement agencies. This feature is reflected in the structure of the apparatus, the methods and forms of implementation of their functions and other features of the legal status.

The system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at establishing and maintaining law and order in society, both in relation to citizens and organizations.

On September 16, 2016, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyev signed Law No. 407 “On Internal Affairs Bodies”, adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis on August 12 and approved by the Senate on August 24. The law establishes that the Ministry of Internal Affairs reports directly to the President, and on certain issues in accordance with the law - to the Cabinet of Ministers. The Minister of the Interior is approved by the President on the proposal of the Prime Minister and dismissed by the President. Deputy Ministers are appointed and dismissed by the President.

The main tasks of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan are the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, ensuring the rule of law, the security of the individual, society and the state, as well as the prevention and prevention of offenses[3].

Article 4 The internal affairs bodies, within their competence, carry out activities in the following main areas:

- ❖ protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens;
- ❖ protection of public order and ensuring public safety;
- ❖ carrying out pre-investigation checks, operational-search activities, carrying out inquiries and preliminary investigations in criminal cases;
- ❖ combating crime and terrorism, including by participating in the suppression of acts of terrorism and the release of hostages, as well as combating human trafficking;
- ❖ prevention of offenses, identification and elimination of the causes and conditions that contribute to them, identification of persons prone to committing offenses;
- enforcement of preventive measures, criminal punishment and other measures of criminal law influence, as well as the organization of work on the search for persons;
- ❖ Proceedings on cases of administrative offenses, execution of decisions on the application of administrative penalties;
- ❖ ensuring road safety;
- ❖ ensuring the fulfillment of the requirements of the passport system, the implementation of work on the issuance and execution of documents necessary for exit and entry into the Republic of Uzbekistan, permits for permanent and temporary residence, control over compliance with the passport system and the rules of stay on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- ❖ control in the sphere of circulation of civilian and service weapons and ammunition for them, explosive materials for industrial use, as well as pyrotechnic products, narcotic drugs, their analogues, psychotropic substances and precursors;
- ❖ implementation of forensic activities;
- ❖ protection of state, especially important, categorized and other objects, property of individuals and legal entities;

❖ licensing and issuance of permits, as well as control over compliance with license and permit requirements and conditions;

- implementation of military mobilization work and measures for civil protection;
- Participation in legislative activities and work to improve legal awareness and legal culture in society.

RESULTS.

In today's world, efficiency is becoming a must for people and organizations. However, in order to survive, thrive, stand out, and lead in the new reality that Stephen Covey calls the new Age of the Knowledge Worker, we must move beyond it with efficiency. A new era in the history of mankind requires the achievement of greatness. It calls for us to develop our abilities, pursue our goals with passion, and make a significant contribution to the world around us.

In today's world, the effectiveness of a person or organization is not a matter of choice, today it is a prerequisite - the price of an entrance ticket to the playing field. And in order to survive, create something new, achieve excellence and be a leader in this new reality, it is not enough just to become effective, we must achieve more. The new age demands greatness from us—self-actualization, passionate performance, and meaningful contribution[2].

At present, a number of laws and orders have been adopted that have radically changed the management system, recruitment, service, evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities of the internal affairs bodies. In particular, the Minister of Internal Affairs signed an order “On approval of the Instruction on the procedure for organizing and conducting events for the selection of candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies”[4].

The document was adopted in accordance with the Decree of the President dated November 29, 2017 No. PP-3413 “On measures to radically improve the procedure for working with personnel of internal affairs bodies and organizing their service.”

According to the Instruction, candidates are accepted for service on a voluntary basis through selection by internal affairs bodies for available vacancies. The number of candidates participating in the competition is not limited. Athletes who have won national sports competitions in the last five years or won one of the three prizes in international sports competitions are accepted for service solely on the basis of a final interview. Candidates wishing to enter the service must apply to the internal affairs body at the place of permanent residence with an appropriate application.

Competitions include the following stages:

- preliminary study (verification of compliance with the requirements established by the Regulations and these Instructions);
- assessment of physical fitness;
- assessment of the level of intellectual development and psycho-emotional stability;
- final interview.

DISCUSSION

In connection with the adoption of the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in order to further strengthen state control over compliance with budgetary legislation and targeted spending of budgetary funds of the budgetary system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as systematization of the norms, regulations and powers of participants in financial control, the relevant orders of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the

procedure for conducting and the position of the Control and Revision Inspectorate of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan[5].

This Regulation defines the tasks, functions, rights, responsibilities and organizational framework for the activities of the control and audit inspection of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter - the CAI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs) and control and audit inspections in the Department of Corrections of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent.

The control and revision inspection is a structural subdivision of the central office of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is directly subordinate to the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

CAI MIA has departments of control and audit inspections in the Department of Execution of Punishments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent without the status of a legal entity, which in their activities report directly to the CAI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The CAI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the departments of control and audit inspections in the Department of Execution of Punishments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent are guided in their activities by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, resolutions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions and orders Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, other legislative acts and these Regulations.

The CAI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the departments of control and audit inspections in the Department for the Execution of Punishments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent are the state financial control over the targeted use of the funds of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the budgets of state trust funds and extra-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations.

CAI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and departments of control and audit inspections in the Department for the Execution of Punishments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, they carry out, if necessary, unscheduled audits and checks.

The staff of the CAI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and departments of control and audit inspections in the Department of Corrections of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent is staffed from among highly qualified specialists with sustainable life principles, and young professionally trained graduates of economic and financial higher educational institutions with experience in this field for at least 3 years.

The control and audit check is carried out on the basis of the principles of legality, objectivity, independence and individuality, the personal responsibility of each employee for the status of the assigned work tasks and the performance of individual tasks.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to note that the main goal of the activities of the control and audit inspections is control over financial and material flows related to contractual and procurement activities. CAI employees are also responsible for preventing losses and unjustified expenses. Therefore, the effectiveness of the management of these units will entail the prevention

of financial violations and the maintenance of general control over the financial departments of the units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

To date, according to the task set 12/1-2022 dated On May 11, 2022, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan developed an order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 21, 2022 No. 232 “On the introduction of a system for assessing the performance of the heads of structural and territorial facilities of the Department of Financial and Logistics and the Control and Audit Inspectorate of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan”[6].

According to this order, the charter and procedure for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of the heads of structural and territorial facilities of the Department of Financial and Logistics and the Control and Audit Inspectorate of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved.

CAI development is not an easy process that requires complex theoretical knowledge and sufficient experience from employees. Thanks to CAI, the organization rewards the employee for achieving the desired results, which in turn are an element of strategic management.

It is worth noting that today, not all organizations are ready to practice the system in question. Usually in such organizations it is possible to evaluate the work of personnel only from a subjective point of view. However, in order to visualize how law enforcement officers gave their best according to a full-fledged program, then it is better to use the CAI system, which will make it possible to understand how effective the activities of the internal affairs bodies are. Another important point is that CAI provides an opportunity to learn about employees who are inefficient. This is the importance and feature of the CAI system, that the indicators in it can be easily changed and tracked over time.

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